

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Los Angeles
Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia

IMPROVING SCHOOL NURSE CONFIDENCE WITH CONTINUOUS GLUCOSE
MONITORING TECHNOLOGY

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) offers reliable glycemic measurements and improved health outcomes for pediatric patients with Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus (T1D). With CGM use becoming the new pediatric standard of care for T1D management, it is increasingly common for children with diabetes to arrive in school wearing CGM devices. School nurses' lack of familiarity with this new technology can lead to dangerous methods of assessment, interpretation, and treatment of sensor glucose results in the school environment. This project aimed to increase confidence among school nurses in providing accurate and safe treatment decisions for students with T1D by developing and evaluating an evidence-based, standardized CGM protocol. A total of 22 school nurses were recruited to complete an adapted Diabetes Device Confidence Scale, assessing their confidence in operating CGM devices before and after exposure to a standardized CGM assessment protocol. Results revealed an overall increase in confidence related to CGM knowledge, use, and assessment following observation of an educational module detailing a standardized approach to CGM assessment tailored to school nurses. Open-ended responses from participants were additionally gathered to identify barriers and facilitators for implementation of this protocol into clinical practice. This project highlights the potential of a standardized assessment tool for school nurses to increase their confidence in caring for students with CGMs at school, informing future integration of CGM training into clinical practice guidelines to promote safe and accurate treatment decisions for students with T1D at school.

Keywords: school nurse, type 1 diabetes, T1D, continuous glucose monitoring, CGM

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

From an early age, my parents instilled in me the importance of education. Their engagement in my schooling, from volunteering in my elementary school classrooms to re-reading every last draft of my university admissions essays, provided me with the confidence, knowledge, and skills to succeed in all levels of my education and career. My academic accomplishments are a reflection of their selfless and enduring devotion to my sister and I. To my parents-Thank you for offering us every opportunity in life.

Background

Continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) devices have developed in recent years into reliable forms of glycemic measurement for patients with Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus (T1D). Randomized controlled trials have demonstrated that the use of CGM technology positively impacts the glycemic values of children, adolescents, and adults living with diabetes (Dicembrini et al., 2021; Laffel et al., 2020). Research has also identified that adherence to a CGM treatment regimen improves overall blood glucose trends among youth (Sanderson et al., 2021). This evidence suggests that the technological advancements of CGM devices have the potential to positively impact the 83% of adolescents diagnosed with T1D who still do not fall within the category of optimal blood glucose control (HbA1c value of <7.5%) as identified by the American Diabetes Association (American Diabetes Association [ADA], 2021; Foster et al., 2019).

Diabetes is identified as the third most common chronic health condition in schools, with a prevalence rate of 2.22 for every 1,000 children (Pettitt et al., 2014). The National Association of School Nurses (NASN) recently updated their practice guidelines to include CGM-specific assessment details in accordance with the widespread adoption of real-time CGM technology that has quickly become a fixture of modern diabetes care for school-aged children (Wilt & Jameson, 2021). Though this position is backed by a myriad of evidence suggesting that the operation of CGM devices correlates with improved diabetes care outcomes in the pediatric population, barriers to consistent CGM use in the school environment still exist.

School nurses are the healthcare professionals that school staff rely on to provide accurate treatment decisions for students with T1D. With the rate of CGM adoption among children younger than 12 years of age increasing 10-fold since 2012, the use of technological

devices to treat pediatric diabetes mellitus is becoming commonplace in the school environment (Foster et al., 2019). Incorporating CGMs in school settings is a challenge due to nurses' identified lack of familiarity and comfort with the devices (Petrie et al., 2017). Additionally, school nurses report that district policies that have not been updated to reflect the capacity of CGM technology often prevent these devices in the classroom, deterring appropriate use and conflicting with modern diabetes treatment. As such, nonstandardized methods of CGM assessment, interpretation, and implementation by nurses into a school's diabetes management protocol are a clinical practice problem. To keep up with the newest standard of care for pediatric patients with diabetes, it is recommended that clear guidelines and boundaries be established to ensure appropriate CGM use while at school (March et al., 2020)

Clinical Practice Problem

Public school districts do not possess a standardized policy and procedure for school nurses to accurately assess and utilize CGM technology in the school environment. School nurses' variable method for interpreting CGM readings jeopardizes the quality of care for the students with diabetes who wear these devices in public schools each day. Variation in blood glucose monitoring assessments by school nurses, caused by a district's lack of a standardized policy and procedure, is a systemic factor that leads to a lack of confidence among nurses regarding their ability to provide students with appropriate diabetes treatment, as indicated by CGM results.

Project Purpose

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project is to increase confidence among school nurses in providing accurate and safe treatment decisions for students with T1D by

developing and evaluating an evidence-based, standardized CGM protocol for use by school nurses.

Supporting Frameworks

Framework for 21st Century School Nursing Practice

The Framework for 21st Century School Nursing Practice serves as an overarching guide for school nurses to improve current standards of practice in the school environment. This model depicts four main principles of school nursing practice: care coordination, leadership, quality improvement, and community/population health. These elements holistically link student health and safety to school nursing standards of practice (NASN, 2020). The gathered evidence for this DNP project was used to create a standardized policy and procedure for districtwide adoption that school nurses can follow when providing care to students with diabetes who wear CGM sensors. Introducing evidence-based policies and procedures to improve the quality of student health employs the core principles of leadership, care coordination, and quality improvement to promote student health. This project aimed to improve school nurses' confidence in safely and effectively providing care to students who wear CGMs during the school day. This outcome strengthened the foundational standards of practice that visually encompass the 21st Century School Nursing Practice framework (Figure 1).

Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice

Overview

In addition to the Framework for 21st Century School Nursing Practice, this project was guided by the validated framework of the revised Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice (Figure 2). This model utilizes a multi-step approach to propose, implement, and sustain evidence-based practice changes. This framework, consisting of seven steps and three

distinguishable decision points, has been successfully applied to quality improvement interventions in the healthcare sector since its introduction in 1994 (Buckwalter et al., 2017). While no school nursing-specific studies employed this model, a variety of projects have demonstrated the successful use of this framework in outpatient pediatric and adolescent care settings. One recent example is the use of the Iowa Model to expand evidence-based practice changes for pediatric health beyond the confines of the hospital environment (Schutte et al., 2022). Using the Iowa framework to ensure that nurses serving as clinical providers in the community are cognizant of and adhering to the latest practice standards is one way to ensure that quality improvement processes are effectively implemented. The guiding framework of the Iowa Model can be adopted in the school environment to integrate evidence-based practice changes for nurses who serve pediatric populations in the school setting.

Identifying Triggering Issues and Opportunities

The first step of the Iowa Model is to identify a triggering issue or opportunity (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). The varied, nonstandardized method of interpreting CGM readings among school nurses is a major safety concern for T1D students, who rely upon school nursing assessment to treat their suspected hypoglycemia and hyperglycemia. School nurses who lack confidence in CGM assessment skills risk interpreting the glycemic sensor values inaccurately, which was identified as an issue of concern for school nursing practice.

State the Question or Purpose

The second step of the Iowa Model is to state the purpose of the practice change to address the triggering issue (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). In this context, the purpose of this project was to prioritize establishing a policy and procedure for school nurses to reference when assessing CGM results.

First Decision Point

The Iowa Model then requires users to consider whether or not this topic is a priority for the organization in question. This decision point ensures that the pursuit of the evidence-based practice change is worth the time, resources, and effort needed for implementation (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). Addressing low confidence in making assessment decisions based on CGM data by school nurses was identified as a priority for the organization since it aligns with the organizational goal of protecting student safety.

Form a Team

Facilitating buy-in from a group is required to support the implementation of a project (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). A team of key stakeholders, including school district-employed Credentialed School Nurses were engaged to lend their support in the context of this doctoral project.

Assemble, Appraise, and Synthesize Body of Evidence

Systematically, a thorough literature review is conducted to collect, analyze, and interpret the existing evidence published on the topic (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). The literature was synthesized from peer-reviewed research journals and clinical practice guidelines on CGM technology use and school nurses' role in treating patients with T1D who wear sensor glucose devices. Each publication's evidence level was determined to continue to the second decision point of the Iowa Model process.

Second Decision Point

At this stage, sufficient evidence must exist prior to initiating a plan for practice change. This decision point requires additional research to gather data if high-quality evidence in the area of interest is lacking (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). Based on the results of the

literature review, it was determined whether sufficient evidence exists in support of a standard of practice change in the field of school nursing for CGM interpretation.

Design and Pilot the Practice Change

Next, the practice change was designed and piloted to determine areas for improvement before full-scale implementation in the organization. These steps involve planning, data collection, and evaluation to identify additional resources, opportunities for stakeholder engagement, and organizational needs to facilitate performance (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). The practice change of designing a novel policy and procedure for CGM assessment by school nurses required the collective synthesis of existing standardized CGM protocols, professional organization care guidelines, and pediatric care standards for diabetes treatment. The content of the deliverable policy and procedure was specifically designed to address the gaps in provider knowledge about glycemic sensors identified by the literature. The newly designed CGM protocol was evaluated by a number of school nurses to elicit feedback and suggestions for improvement prior to wide scale dissemination.

Third Decision Point

The third and final decision point is to determine if the proposal is appropriate for adoption (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). In alignment with the Iowa Model, the collected data and feedback from the initial iteration of this CGM protocol in the piloted cohort concluded that this change is appropriate for sustained adoption.

Integrate and Sustain the Practice Change

The Iowa Model stresses the importance of project sustainability. This step of integrating and sustaining the practice change is integral to ensuring that the intervention remains applicable and operable for future use (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). The plan to sustain the

standardized CGM protocol was to ensure that school nurses are regularly briefed on the practice change through recurrent email and health staff communications. Once implemented into districts, this CGM policy and procedure can additionally be evaluated by nurse teams during periodic staff meetings with administrators.

Disseminate Results

The last step of the Iowa Model is to share the results of the interventional practice change with the public, relevant stakeholders, interested parties, and additional researchers (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). This dissemination of the policy and procedure to standardize methods of interpreting CGM readings was done via the creation of a poster and PowerPoint presentation that is presented at local and statewide school nursing conferences. Handouts and links to electronic resources are also distributed to presentation attendees and individuals interested in the topic. Reaching out to the California School Nurses Organization is another way to disseminate this information through electronic means to school nurses practicing throughout the state through their membership base. The organization can email the project documents to school nurse members in their periodic newsletter. Figure 3 visually depicts the steps of the Iowa Model regarding this DNP project proposal.

Review of Literature

The purpose of this DNP project was to increase confidence among school nurses in providing accurate and safe treatment decisions for students with T1D by developing an evidence-based, standardized CGM protocol. A review of the literature allows for the collection and synthesis of evidence to identify common themes that support the proposed DNP project. Literature was synthesized from peer-reviewed journals and clinical practice guidelines on the topic of CGM technology use and school nurses' role in treating patients with T1D who wear CGM devices. All articles included in this literature review were generated from the scholarly databases Public/Publisher MEDLINE (PubMed) and Cumulated Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL). Search terms, such as "CGM," "continuous glucose monitoring," "adherence," "barriers," "diabetes technology," "diabetes," "school nurses," "school," and "type 1 diabetes" were utilized in a variety of combinations to yield a search of literature relevant to the topic of interest. During a preliminary literature search, the terms "children" and "youth" yielded only one result. These qualifying terms were, thus, excluded in subsequent searches to allow for a more extensive view of the literature. Search criteria included studies published between 2018-2023, in English, and from peer-reviewed journals. A total of seven research studies met the search criteria. Of the articles selected for this paper, all consisted of different study methodologies that were ranked according to Grove and Gray's (2019) hierarchy of evidence for nursing research (Table 1, Table 2). The quantitative literature included three observational/descriptive studies and one article that used a quasi-experimental design. All three qualitative publications were of phenomenological design. The themes included in this review of literature are the impact of CGM technology on pediatric glycemic outcomes, provider barriers to accurate CGM assessment, and school nurses' confidence in using these devices.

CGM Impact on Glycemic Outcomes

The studies by Farfel et al. (2020), Tanenbaum et al. (2021), and Pickup et al. (2015) demonstrate strong evidence to suggest that CGM technology correlates with positive glycemic outcomes for users, thus increasing adherence to CGM device use. The article by Pickup et al. (2015) provides qualitative data through exemplar quotes from participants that express how CGMs assist patients in obtaining lower HbA1c values, better blood glucose control, and less glycemic variability. Farfel et al. (2020) report that patients' satisfaction with the glycemic improvements that CGM devices cultivate leads to greater adherence to CGM treatment over time. This positive correlation between CGM satisfaction and adherence is statistically supported by a p-value of <0.001 (Farfel et al., 2020). Tanenbaum et al. (2021) establish the strongest support for this concept by experimentally demonstrating that CGM use increases the "time spent in range" of participants' sensor glucose values between 70-180 mg/dL during the day. No contradictory findings were identified in this synthesis of the literature in terms of improved glycemic control for pediatric patients who use CGMs.

Based on the consensus demonstrated within included studies, standards of care for pediatric patients with T1D have been altered to account for the positive impact that CGM technology has on patients' glycemic values. Clinical practice guidelines by the American Association of Clinical Endocrinology, ADA, and National Institute for Health and Care Excellence in the United Kingdom have been recently updated to reflect the new practice standard that all pediatric patients with T1D be started on CGM therapy following diagnosis (Grunberger et al., 2021; ADA, 2021; Mulvihill et al., 2022). This standard of care change has been supported by the Association of Diabetes Care and Education Specialists (Cox et al., 2021). The collective evidence and recent changes to the standards of care for pediatric patients with

diabetes suggest that school nurses, who serve as the sole healthcare providers in the school environment, will be expected to accurately interface with CGM technology as school-aged children with T1D attend school wearing these devices with greater frequency. This is a safety concern that must be addressed since no clear operational guidance or training exists for school nurses to reference when students bring CGM devices to school (March et al., 2020).

Barriers to Accurate CGM Assessment

Factors that serve as the most common barriers to accurately assessing CGM results were consistently identified throughout the literature. Researchers Farfel et al. (2020) and Pickup et al. (2015) reported that sensor alarms dissuade proper CGM use, causing confusion, misinterpretation, and user distress due to their frequency and disruption of daily activities of living. Given that the primary populations studied were school-aged children, the results of the collective evidence can be generalized to infer that the impact of these alarms disrupts students' classroom activities during the school day. Borges and Kubiak (2016) linked this alarm fatigue with the concept of information overload caused by the expanse of sensor data collected and displayed for patients and providers to independently review. The researchers reported a statistically significant negative correlation between participants' perceptions of information overload and their intention to continue using CGM devices as accurately instructed by their diabetes care (Borges & Kubiak, 2016). In their quasi-experimental study, Tanenbaum et al. (2021) provides the strongest currently available evidence of provider barriers to CGM interpretation through its focus on addressing the factors of data explanation, the intended meanings of alarms, and strategies for device use in the experimental implementation of electronically-accessible support for new CGM users. These studies provide moderate to strong evidence to suggest that barriers to CGM interpretation are associated with the technological

limitations of the devices, the data that the CGMs express, and the method in which these devices communicate this data to users (Farfel et al., 2020; Pickup et al., 2015; Borges & Kubiak, 2016; Tanenbaum et al., 2021).

CGM Confidence Among School Nurses

It has been well documented that pediatric patients are transitioning to CGM devices quickly after a T1D diagnosis thanks to the strong evidence supporting their glycemic benefits (Erie et al., 2017; Farfel et al., 2020; March et al., 2020; Tanenbaum et al., 2021; Sanderson et al., 2021). Tanenbaum et al. (2021) reports that CGM use has steadily increased in recent years, with routine use by pediatric patients corresponding directly with individuals' accessibility to CGM supplies. Many healthcare providers are now routinely prescribing CGM devices to patients, regardless of age and length of time since diagnosis, to align with clinical practice guideline changes in the diabetes care sector (ADA, 2021; Cox et al., 2021; Grunberger et al., 2021; Mulvihill et al., 2022).

March et al. (2020) identified that the school nursing field is adapting slowly to the use of modern diabetes devices in the pediatric population. Rapid adoption of CGM technology by newly diagnosed patients leaves school nurses with minimal time to gain appropriate knowledge or attend formal educational sessions on CGM use before the student returns to school following their T1D diagnosis (March et al., 2020). In addition, the responsibility for educating school nurses on how to use the available technology has not yet been established or standardized throughout practice (Wilt & Jameson, 2021). Borges and Kubiak (2016) and March et al. (2020) conclude that there is no clear clinical guidance for nurses to reference when students bring CGM devices to school. Though NASN guidelines list that the use of diabetes care technologies, such as CGMs, for T1D students are a competency that school nurses should master within the

domain of education and training, no physical materials or virtual training modules are available for school nurses to view (Wilt & Jameson, 2021). Minimal evidence exists to directly address the extent that this gap in provider training has on the health outcomes of T1D students.

School nurses need a method to improve their CGM device knowledge and skills in order to boost their confidence in managing students with T1D at school. March et al. (2022) used a pre-and post-intervention survey to conclude that school nurses' confidence in assessing CGM data increased following the electronic dissemination of educational materials about CGM technology and its relationship to types of connected devices, such as smartphones and insulin pumps. Confidence was evaluated using the Diabetes Device Confidence Scale (DDCS), a validated measurement tool that quantifies school nurses' confidence in operating diabetes devices (March et al., 2022). Similarly, Erie et al. (2017) analyzed the experience of remote CGM use by parents and daytime caregivers of children with diabetes at home and in school. In researching the impact that remote CGM monitoring has on caregivers of children with diabetes, surveyed school nursing participants reported that CGM use in schools increased peace of mind, though technological difficulties and frustrations with device interpretation were perceived by the adult users. This project, and the collective literature synthesized above, directly informs this proposed DNP project by supporting the implementation of an electronic CGM protocol for school nurses that explains alarm features, simplifies the interpretation of sensor data, and models a standardized glycemic assessment procedure to increase school nurse confidence in managing the care of T1D students at school.

The content from his body of evidence informs policy development by identifying school nursing-specific limitations in the diabetes management of students at school. For healthcare providers tasked with assessing CGM sensor data, such as school nurses, these specific

limitations to accurate interpretation can manifest as assessment errors, misinterpretation, and a lack of confidence in operating CGM devices (Erie et al., 2017). Specific knowledge gaps among clinical providers exist in regard to indications for glycemic sensor calibration, manual blood glucose fingerstick to confirm CGM accuracy, and interventions required in response to sensor alarms (March et al., 2020; Farfel et al., 2020; Pickup et al., 2015).

Summary of Literature Review

This review of literature aimed to synthesize evidence about the glycemic outcomes and barriers to accurate CGM use for pediatric T1D patients. The research studies demonstrate strong and consistent evidence that CGMs improve glycemic control, supporting standards of practice updates that have led to an influx of pediatric CGM users. While there is an identified positive impact for students who wear CGM devices at school, there are factors that inhibit accurate CGM assessment from the perspective of providers. Barriers to accurate CGM assessment are consistently demonstrated as being technological in nature, though data regarding the impact of these barriers are unlikely to be substantiated without the lens of additional experimental studies among the target population of school nurses who serve T1D students. The research indicates the need for a proposed intervention to address CGM assessment and interpretation for school nurses, informed by the policy development parameters set forth by the NASN clinical practice guidelines for the care of students with T1D. The components of this protocol, as identified in the literature, should aim to address the following topics: types of pediatric CGM devices and their relationship to linked technology, instructions for sensor glucose assessment and alarm interpretation, indications for use of manual blood glucose testing equipment, and technological procedures for sensor calibration. This DNP project will address this issue by proposing

guidance in the form of a standardized practice protocol to improve patient care outcomes related to CGM interpretation in the school setting.

Methods

Low confidence caused by a nonstandardized approach to CGM assessment among school nurses jeopardizes the safety of students with diabetes at school, making this triggering issue a priority for school health professionals whose mission is to promote student safety above all else. Enacting a sustainable practice change to address concerns about school nurses' gaps in glycemic sensor knowledge is considered worth the time, resources, and effort needed for implementation. This DNP project aims to increase confidence among school nurses in providing accurate and safe treatment decisions for students with T1D by developing and evaluating an evidence-based, standardized CGM protocol.

Design

An evidence-based practice approach was used to meet the aims of this project. Pre- and post-adapted Diabetes Device Confidence Scales (DDCS) and open-ended questions related to barriers and facilitators for implementation of a standardized CGM protocol, recommendations for improvement of the protocol, and confidence in caring for students with CGMs helped meet the project's objective of assessing school nurse confidence in providing accurate and safe treatment decisions for students with T1D.

Participants

To reach a target population of school nurses, the primary investigator engaged students in the California State University, Fullerton (CSUF) School Nurse Services Credential (SNSC) Program. The CSUF Credentialing Program comprises approximately 120 students who are professionally employed as registered nurses serving public schools throughout the State of California. Participants were selected through purposive sampling to recruit bachelors-prepared, registered nurses who possess a preliminary SNSC, practice within school settings, are actively

enrolled in the CSUF SNSC program, and are currently caring for, or have past experience caring for, a minimum of one T1D student who wears a CGM while at school. As such, this particular sample consists of clinical care providers who are less than five years into the course of their experience as school nurses, capturing fresh perspectives and feedback from professionals at the beginning of their careers. These sampling criteria aim to exclude registered nurses who do not possess a preliminary SNSC as recognized by the California Commission on Teacher Credentialing, are not currently enrolled as students in an academic institution, and who have no prior experience working with T1D students who wear CGM devices at school.

Implementation of this project involved engaging the following organizational stakeholders: Faculty Director of the CSUF SNSC program, Director of the School of Nursing at CSUF, and the primary investigator's assigned DNP Faculty Advisor. After obtaining the academic contact information for SNSC students from CSUF faculty, the project aims, objectives, procedures, and expectations were shared as part of the recruitment process via an email listserv sent to all enrolled SNSC students. Informed consent was obtained electronically through Qualtrics software from eligible participants prior to beginning project procedures.

School nurses' professional culture is to protect student safety. DNP project members thus anticipate a general receptiveness to this project's initiative to improve the confidence school nurses possess in safely caring for students who use CGM technology at school, without the need to monetarily incentive participation. With stakeholder buy-in, the policy to standardize CGM assessment, as detailed in Appendix A, was expected to align with the School of Nursing's organizational mission of promoting student and staff safety, health, and wellbeing. Since no funds need to be secured to facilitate this project, the proposed project processes were expected to commence at the start of the Fall 2023 school year after obtaining formal CSUF IRB approval.

Setting

All project procedures were conducted virtually, with all organizational communication occurring through email messages between the principal investigator and participants. In aligning with this standard for virtual communication, all materials and information related to recruiting participants, using the CGM protocol, and measuring confidence after product distribution was sent to applicable participants through electronic means. School nurses were introduced to the CGM policy expectations and step-by-step procedural instructions by accessing an online educational video recorded by the principal investigator. This video explained in detail the CGM protocol with hyperlinks to protocol documents. Similar to all materials, it was disseminated to participants through virtual communication pathways, such as email.

Operationalization of Variables and Measures

The outcome measured was school nurses' confidence in performing the skills needed to safely and accurately assess the CGM data of diabetic students at school. Confidence was defined in this context as an individual's self-efficacy or perception of their readiness and ability to perform a specified skill (March et al., 2022). Since this DNP project addresses school nurses' subjective perceptions of their own confidence in assessing CGM results, this construct was operationalized through an adapted version of the Diabetes Device Confidence Scale (DDCS). The DDCS is a 28-item, reliable, validated tool created to measure subjects' self-assessment of their comfort in manipulating diabetes devices, such as sensor-integrated insulin pumps and CGMs (March et al., 2022). School nurses' confidence in providing care to students with CGMs was measured using this DDCS scale, adapted with developers' approval for concision and clarity, to only include fourteen questions specifically related to glycemic sensor technology (Appendix C). Direct permission to adapt the DDCS from the primary researcher who developed

the tool was received by the primary investigator via email (C. March, personal communication, April 16, 2023).

Procedures

Participant Recruitment

The SNSC students were sent an invitation to participate in this project via electronic mail. An announcement was also posted within the general SNSC student Canvas Community. The email and announcement provided informed consent information and a link to the demographic survey, pre-DDCS survey, educational module, protocol, post-DDCS survey, and open-ended questions accessible on any mobile device or computer. The project lead's contact information was provided to participants for help regarding any technical or access issues.

Prior to commencing project procedures, the purpose of the project was shared with participants and participants were prompted by Qualtrics software to electronically sign informed consent. It was explicitly expressed to participants that the opportunity to ask questions to the Primary Investigator will be honored at all times. Additionally, participants were informed that there is no direct benefit and minimal risk associated with participating in this project.

Participation in this project aligns with school nurses' professional culture to protect student safety above all else, thus, individuals' participation was expected to further the societal mission of promoting student and staff safety, health, and wellbeing by improving the confidence school nurses possess in safely caring for students who use CGM technology at school. Risk was minimized through informed consent procedures, open communication with the primary investigator, and de-identifying data in order to maintain participant privacy and confidentiality.

Surveys

Upon volunteering to participate, subjects were directed to consent by clicking the button to begin the demographic survey. After completing the demographic and pre-DDCS survey, participants were granted access to the educational module and protocol. Participants dedicated fifteen minutes to completing the surveys and educational module. A post-DDCS survey was completed by participants immediately after the CGM protocol was presented.

Open-ended Questions

Upon completion of the educational module and post-DDCS survey, participants were prompted to complete open-ended questions about the topic being examined. Open-ended questions were asked of participants at the end of the post-survey to elicit feedback related to views, experiences, and perceptions of the CGM protocol, along with any perceived barriers and facilitators to incorporating the standardized CGM protocol into practice (Appendix D). Open-ended questions allowed participants to express opinions in greater detail, providing in-depth, rich, and relevant data.

Participants were asked to provide feedback to identify gaps in content, discuss the protocols' feasibility for use, and offer advice on implementation into their workflow. Participants' responses were downloaded to a computer and de-identified to maintain participant confidentiality. Responses were analyzed to identify themes related to school nurses' reflections to draw reasonable and meaningful conclusions.

Data Collection

Quantitative Data

Survey data was collected anonymously through an electronic Qualtrics survey link sent to participants. All surveys were completed by participants online. Survey data was downloaded from Qualtrics to Microsoft Excel for analysis. Additionally, de-identified demographic data was

collected from all participants to inform investigators of how long the nurse has been practicing as a school nurse, how many schools the nurse manages, how many students with T1D the school nurse cares for, and how many of the school nurses' type 1 diabetic students wear CGMs. These questions informed this project by highlighting the background, breadth of experience, and characteristics of the school settings where these nurses are serving children with type 1 diabetes who wear CGMs.

Qualitative Data

Qualitative data consisted of the statements and comments from participants during open-ended questions in the post-survey. After completion of the open-ended questions, participant responses were downloaded directly to a password-protected computer and de-identified into a Microsoft Word document to maintain participant confidentiality. This qualitative data was collected confidentially, with subject feedback remaining protected and de-identified throughout the project using randomized numerical participant coding (e.g., Participant 1, Participant 2).

Data Analysis

Quantitative data

This project used the statistical capabilities of QI macros software to assess the results of the 14-point Likert scale DDCS surveys in order to measure school nurses' perceived confidence pre- and post-project implementation. Likert scales are commonly employed as the preferred psychometric measure of self-reported, unobservable constructs (Jebb et al., 2021).

Qualitative Data

Open-ended question responses were analyzed to identify common themes from the collected qualitative data using qualitative descriptive methods. A qualitative descriptive methodology makes sense of data collection efforts by categorizing descriptions of phenomena

to better understand underlying experiences and identify common themes in the research (Sandelowski, 2000).

Evaluation Plan

Evaluation of this project's deliverable product compared nurses' confidence in CGM skill acquisition pre- and post-exposure to the developed CGM protocol. Feedback collected from direct users is expected to guide future iterations of the product. Given that this phase of the project was developmental, a robust plan for future evaluation was determined based on the results of the data analysis.

Ethical Considerations

To maintain participant privacy and confidentiality, all survey data was de-identified for use by the investigators. All data, both qualitative and quantitative, was saved in a singular location on the desktop of a personal, password-protected laptop. At the conclusion of this project, data will be saved for a maximum of three years to ensure compliance with federal requirements before being electronically removed and destroyed, deleted from both an encrypted, password-protected folder and the personal laptop's trash.

Institutional Review Board Approval

This project required the institutional approval of CSUF faculty, obtained formally through a letter of support written on CSUF letterhead. Since this DNP project posed no direct risk to participants, it was submitted for expedited review and was approved by the CSUF Institutional Review Board (IRB), which provides consideration for ethical human subject protection.

Results

Demographics

A total of 33 school nurses (n=33) were deemed eligible and consented to participate in the study. Within the study population, most nurses (n=26) were bachelor's prepared, with seven nurses identified as possessing an advanced degree. The majority of participants reported having 2-3 years of practice as school nurses (n=11), with seven nurses reporting 3-4 years of practice, six who have worked only 1-2 years, five who have 4-5 years experience, and four nurses who individually reported a total of >5 years experience in the school nursing field. Most participants reported working in elementary schools located in suburban neighborhoods (n=21), whereas nine nurses served urban communities, and three nurses worked in rural regions. The majority of surveyed school nurses (32%) stated that they are responsible for an assignment of three school sites. At these sites, the majority of school nurses (n=12) reported having 2-3 students with diabetes under their care during the 2022-2023 school year. In further detail, 45% of respondents (n=15) said all of their T1D students used CGM technology at school, 24% (n=8) reported that more than half of all of their students with diabetes had CGMs, 24% reported that less than half of all of their students with diabetes had CGMs (n=8), and 6% (n=2) of school nurses reported that their students did not have a CGM device. When asked to identify the source of their initial training with CGMs, most survey participants reported relying on their nursing colleagues to obtain education (33%), 27% learned about CGM functionality from the family of the student with diabetes, 27% used the internet to independently investigate CGMs, and 6% shared that no CGM-specific training was ever received. Only one participant (3%) reported receiving CGM education from a Certified Diabetes Educator or healthcare provider associated with a hospital

network and only one participant (3%) had a history of attending a formal training session specifically about CGM use in pediatric patients at a professional nursing conference.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data

A total of 22 participants completed the 14-point pre- and post-DDCS surveys. Employing the statistical capabilities of QI macros software, a Likert scale was utilized to identify whether or not there exists a statistically significant difference between participants' DDCS surveys, which measured school nurses' perceived confidence with CGM devices before and after exposure to the CGM protocol and educational module. The null hypothesis of this statistical test was that the standardized CGM protocol and educational module does not cause any statistically significant difference to a participant's confidence in understanding and operating CGM devices worn by T1D students at school. Harnessing the statistical capacities of a two-tailed, paired sample *t*-test, the results indicated that a mean difference between pre- and post-DDCS surveys exists, as stipulated by a *p*-value of <0.001 (Intellectus Statistics, 2023). As such, the null hypothesis is rejected in favor of the understanding that the average pre-DDCS scores, which demonstrate school nurses' confidence with CGM devices prior to observing the standardized CGM protocol, are significantly lower than the mean of the post-DDCS survey responses obtained after exposure to the CGM protocol and educational module (Figure 4).

Qualitative data

Participants offered narrative responses to open-ended questions regarding the barriers and facilitators to implementing the proposed CGM protocol in their district. The primary themes identified included that time constraints were the largest barrier preventing school nurses from pursuing the implementation of a standardized CGM policy and procedure, a protocol that was

already written was the best medium with which to facilitate staff training on the subject, and that administrative support would best serve to reinforce employee adherence to a standardized CGM protocol. Multiple participants acknowledged limitations on time for both nurses and school staff as the main barrier to establishing and maintaining a districtwide CGM protocol. One participant stated that, even if her school district had a standardized policy and procedure, school nurses “lack of time for training.” A different participant said candidly, “New hires and nurses have very little training.” With “not enough time to complete [the training],” as another participant expressed, the CGM protocol would effectively not serve to improve the assessment of sensor glucose readings for students with diabetes at school. Many of these voiced time constraints were attributed to heavy caseloads for both the nurse team and school staff. One participant noted that “many teachers complain they have over 20 students in the classroom but need to pay special attention to the students with diabetes.” This quote demonstrates that school staff who experience juggle multiple responsibilities find it difficult to devote sufficient time and attention to a student’s diabetes care. Fitting in a comprehensive CGM training into an overworked school staff’s schedule was identified by participants as the largest barrier to implementation in a school district.

In terms of the facilitators that assist nurses in implementing a CGM protocol in their practice setting, participants identified that an already drafted policy and procedure, presented in writing as a handout, was the best medium with which to present information to their staff. When asked what would best facilitate implementation of a CGM protocol, a participant responded with, “having it all written out ready to go.” Another participant elaborated, “I would have the 1 page handout at all my sites and use [it] to train my health assistants.” Additionally, participants claimed that administrative support, in the identified roles of lead nurses, program

administrators, assistant superintendents, principals, vice principals, and directors of special education and student support services, would make the most impact in facilitating staff adherence to a districtwide CGM policy and procedure. This data suggests that support from direct supervisors in schools' administrative hierarchies has a great impact on the success of school nurses who attempt to introduce a standardized protocol with the aim of improving their confidence in managing the care of students with diabetes who wear CGM technology at school. According to the narrative responses of the study participants, administrators possess the authority, desire, and resources to enforce adherence to new policies and procedures that impact their employees, improving the successful implementation of a districtwide practice change related to CGM assessment by school nurses. The qualitative themes identified as facilitators and barriers to implementing a CGM protocol into school districts offer a glimpse into the real-world applications of the developed CGM policy and procedure for nurses who currently practice in the school environment.

Discussion

Evaluation of this project's deliverable product compared nurses' increased confidence in CGM skill acquisition post-exposure to the developed CGM protocol. The results of this project highlighted the potential of a standardized assessment tool for school nurses to increase their confidence in caring for students with CGMs at school, informing future integration of CGM training into clinical practice guidelines to promote safe and accurate treatment decisions for students with T1D at school.

Implications

This project has implications for school nursing practice since the data demonstrates that a standardized CGM protocol successfully addresses gaps in glycemic sensor knowledge among school nurses, the components of which can be harnessed to design professional training standards for nurses working with students with T1D in the K-12 school environment.

Qualitative data obtained from participants' feedback to questions about facilitators and barriers to clinical practice implementation is expected to guide future iterations of a standardized CGM protocol. Overall findings from this project indicate that school nursing practice was enhanced by the implementation of a standardized protocol for CGM assessment. Administrative support in the school environment was acknowledged as being an important facilitator in successful protocol implementation. Written policies and procedures were identified as the most successful medium with which to publish a CGM protocol for implementation at a school district level.

Respondents consistently recalled that time constraints were a major barrier to school nurse training, thus indicating the need to implement a CGM protocol that can be referenced quickly and efficiently despite limitations on time. Using this knowledge, future guides can harness this evidence to develop the most appropriate CGM policy and procedure for use by school nurses.

Limitations

With only 33 participants, this study was limited by its small sample size. Only 22 of the 33 participants completed the full pre- and post-DDCS surveys. With this small of a sample size, questionnaire nonresponse bias is a notable concern. This response rate suggests that the quantitative results are potentially skewed in favor of those participants who were most interested in the benefits of the CGM protocol. Additional limitations include participants' self-reported assessment of skills and knowledge. Results obtained from self-administered questionnaires must be viewed in the context of acquiescence and social desirability bias, or the likelihood of study participants to respond with the more advisable or socially preferred answers on a rating scale (Kreitchmann et al., 2019). For example, nurses who know they should possess a basic understanding of CGM functionality may have had a tendency to respond to the administered DDCS survey with answer choices that reflect positively on their professional practice, rather than answer in a manner more consistent with their true knowledge, exposure, skills, and capabilities. Additionally, most respondents work in elementary schools located in suburban environments. This sample of participants is not necessarily reflective of school nurse experiences in other types of communities, both metropolitan or rural. Given that this project was largely developmental, a robust plan for future evaluation must address this project's limitations in order to substantiate the study results.

Recommendations

Recommendations for future research should consider concerns related to this study's participant biases. Designing a study that does not rely upon self-reported survey data collection is the best way circumvent forms of response bias. Future study design should consider the direct observation of school nurses in performing CGM-related tasks in order to best assess school

nurses' individual competencies in operating CGM devices. In addition, future studies should attempt to recruit school nurses with a greater variety of career experience. Due to convenience sampling, this project only captured the perspectives of school nurses who are early in the course of their school nursing careers. As such, recommendations are to collect responses from nurses who have worked for a greater length of time in the school environment, as their professional experiences and acquired knowledge may impact the overall conclusions of this research. Additionally, research should be conducted to measure the real-life impact of the intervention on nurses' assessment decisions and how they relate to improved student outcomes. This would allow for more knowledge about whether the potential benefits of a standardized CGM assessment protocol contribute to evidence in support of a sustained practice change.

Sustainability

Sustainability in the course of this project was considered in order to allow for sustained practice change among participants. The project was designed in order to allow for participants to download accessible materials, such as electronic copies of the standardized CGM protocol and drafted school board policy, during the course of the study. Hyperlinks to the educational module were also shared with the intention of offering participants discretionary access to view and share the module on a free, online platform. These materials were made accessible to participants in the hopes of augmenting any already existing CGM training that occurs at participants' individual places of employment.

Conclusion

This project underscores the importance of providing school nurses with the training and support they need to effectively use CGM technology in managing students with T1D. It also highlights the potential benefits of standardized protocols and educational modules in enhancing

nurses' confidence and competence in this area. It also points to the need to address practical barriers, such as time constraints, to facilitate the successful implementation of such interventions. Further research is needed to explore these issues in more depth and to evaluate the impact of such interventions on student outcomes.

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Appendix A

School District Board Policy

STANDARDIZED CONTINUOUS GLUCOSE MONITORING (CGM) POLICY FOR SCHOOL NURSES

Written Health & Safety Program

POLICY STATEMENT

In accordance with *Education Code* § 3051.12

A standardized Continuous Glucose Monitoring (CGM) protocol for Credentialed School Nurses is hereby established by the Superintendent and Governing Board to coordinate the use of CGM devices for the care of students at school as determined necessary to comply with applicable California Education Code Health and Safety regulations for students with diabetes at school.

This program applies to all California licensed school nurses who provide direct care for diabetic students while on campus, as a requirement of their job duties (Ed. Code § 3051.12, 49423, 49423.6).

RESPONSIBILITIES

CGM Protocol Administrator

A Credentialed School Nurse who possesses a clear School Nurse Services Credential and valid Registered Nursing license in the State of California has been designated as the CGM Protocol Administrator and as such is responsible for:

- Identifying students with diabetes at each school site who utilize CGM technology and require intervention by school staff in order to carry out their individualized health procedures on campus
- Informing applicable nurses responsible for conducting care, as specified by their job description and duties thereafter
- Supervising the proper use of all diabetes supplies and equipment, as it relates to CGM procedures
- Arranging for and/or conducting CGM protocol training
- Assessing school nurse retention of training to ensure that all procedures are administered in accordance with their indicated instruction
- Maintaining all program documentation and participant evaluation results
- Evaluating the program annually
- Updating the written policy and procedure annually, or more frequently as deemed necessary to account for technology updates

Supervisors/School Administrators

Supervisors and school administrators are responsible for ensuring that the program is implemented in their division(s)/school. In addition to being knowledgeable about the program requirements, supervisors and school administrators must also ensure that the program is understood and followed by the school nurses under their direction. Duties of supervisors and school administrators include:

- Support the training and evaluation
- Schedule time for employee training
- Ensuring that employees under their supervision (including new hires) have received appropriate training and evaluation, per department protocol
- Enforcing the proper implementation of the CGM protocol and adherence to general safety protocols, as necessary

Employees

In accordance with *Education Code* § 3051.12

Employees have a responsibility to conduct all procedures, diabetes care tasks, and medication administration in the manner in which they are trained. Credentialed School Nurses and appropriate licensed personnel must also:

- Care for students with diabetes as instructed
- Administer all medication and diabetes care procedures when appropriately indicated
- Maintain a responsibility to abide by all district policy and procedures, in accordance with this protocol, at all times
- Immediately inform their supervisor or the program administrator of any questions regarding the care of a student with diabetes and inform their supervisor should any additional concerns arise during the course of their duties

CGM PROCEDURE

The CGM procedure will cover the following topics:

- Types of pediatric CGM devices and associated technology
- Sensor glucose assessment procedures
- Alarm interpretation instructions
- Indications for use of manual blood glucose testing equipment
- Procedures for sensor calibration

Employees are responsible for understanding and complying at all times with the contents of this CGM procedure, as designated by California Education Code Health and Safety regulations.

EVALUATION

The Program Administrator will monitor the effectiveness and compliance with this standardized protocol by:

- Frequent unscheduled observations of employee activities in the work environment to confirm proper diabetes care to students is being provided
- Observation of a return demonstration for skills to confirm accurate diabetes care procedures

Any program finding concerns by supervisors or school administrators will be reported to the Program Administrator immediately. The Program Administrator shall maintain a record of program findings and remedial training actions taken and/or anticipated dates for remedial training action implementation.

DOCUMENTATION

A written copy of this protocol is to be kept in the Program Administrator's office, electronically in the Districtwide Google Suite, and available to all employee training participants who wish to review it.

The Program Administrator shall maintain the records for a period of 7 calendar years, per school board policy.

Appendix B

School District Board Procedure

Figure 1

School District Board Procedure

CGM Procedure for School Nurses

Continuous Glucose Monitoring (CGM) Assessment Guidelines

What do the arrows mean?	Possible Adjustments:
Glucose could increase more than 90 mg/dL in 30 minutes.	Current glucose plus 100 mg/dL .
Glucose could increase 60-90 mg/dL in 30 minutes.	Current glucose plus 75 mg/dL .
Glucose could increase 30-60 mg/dL in 30 minutes.	Current glucose plus 50 mg/dL .
Steady. Not increasing/decreasing more than 1 mg/dL each minute.	No adjustment.
Glucose could decrease 30-60 mg/dL in 30 minutes.	Current glucose minus 50 mg/dL .
Glucose could decrease 60-90 mg/dL in 30 minutes.	Current glucose minus 75 mg/dL .
Glucose could decrease more than 90 mg/dL in 30 minutes.	Current glucose minus 100 mg/dL .

 Hypoglycemia treatment indicated if <70 mg/dL

 Alarms that require manual fingerstick to confirm glycemic result:

No Alerts or Alarm

Sensor Error

Don't remove sensor.
Temporary issue. Wait up to 3 hours.

Help

Signal Loss

Attempting to reconnect. Wait up to 30 minutes.

Help

Urgent Low Glucose Alarm

OK

 Hypoglycemia treatment indicated if Low <70 mg/dL

Additional Tips for Successful School Use

- CGM has a lag time so rechecks 15 min after a low BG should be with a fingerstick
- Alarms must be acknowledged separately on both CGM device (phone or receiver) & insulin pump
- Routine CGM device calibration is no longer indicated for Dexcom g6 or g7 devices

Note. Procedure for CGM assessment tailored to school nurses.

Appendix C

Table 1: CGM Device Confidence Scale

Table 1

CGM Device Confidence Scale

Rate your confidence in performing the following tasks or skills with diabetes devices independently	Not at all confident	Somewhat confident	Moderately confident	Very confident	Extremely confident
1. I understand what a sensor-integrated insulin pump is					
2. I can operate a student's sensor-integrated pump if needed					
3. I can operate a student's CGM if needed					
4. I know when to calibrate and when not to calibrate a CGM					
5. I can monitor the CGM tracing/graph when needed					
6. I can interpret trend arrows on a CGM tracing					
7. I understand what the different CGM alarms mean					
8. I recognize when to test a glucose using a meter for a student with a CGM					
9. I can adequately assess a student's knowledge about their CGM					
10. I can help a teacher/other school staff understand what to do if a student's CGM alarms in class					
11. I can help a student manage their diabetes with a variety of CGMs					
12. I can learn how to use a diabetes device that I am not familiar with					
13. I can set expectations for device use in school with parents					
14. I can easily find resources to teach school staff about diabetes devices					

Note. Adapted from March et al. (2022) Diabetes Device Confidence Scale.

Appendix D

Table 2: Open-Ended Survey Questions

Table 2

Open-Ended Survey Questions

Open-ended questions for participants to complete:
1. What barriers do you see would prevent you from implementing this protocol in your district?
2. What facilitators would assist you with implementing this protocol in your district?
3. What recommendations do you have to increase the usefulness of this tool?
4. Describe how access to this protocol would impact your confidence, positively or negatively, in providing care to students with CGMs?

Note. Participant responses made up the qualitative data analysis.

Appendix E

Table 3: Paired Sample *t*-Test

Table 3

Paired Sample t-Test for the Difference Between Pre and Post Survey Data

Pre Survey		Post Survey		<i>t</i> -Test	<i>p</i> -value
<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
2.15	0.91	2.89	0.72	-8.75	< 0.001

Note. Table of pre and post survey averages, standard deviations, *t*-test, & *p*-value.

Appendix F

Bar Plot of Pre and Post Survey Means

Figure 2

Bar Plot of Pre and Post Survey Means

Note. Bar plot of pre and post survey means with 95% confidence interval error bars.